

An end to end workflow for synthetic data generation for robust object detection*

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Abstract—Object detection is a task in computer vision that involves detecting instances of visual objects of a particular class in digital images. Numerous computer vision tasks highly depend on object detection such as instance segmentation, image captioning and object tracking. A major purpose of object detection is to develop computational models that provide inputs crucial to computer vision applications. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have recently become popular due to their key roles in enabling object detection. However, the performance of CNNs is largely dependent upon the quality and quantity of training datasets, which are often difficult to obtain in real-world applications. In order to ensure the robustness of such models, it is vital that training instances are provided under various randomized conditions. These conditions are typically a combination of a variety of factors, including lighting conditions, object location, the presence of multiple objects in the scene, varieties of backgrounds, and the angle of the camera. In particular, companies, depending on their applications (such as fault detection, anomaly detection, condition monitoring, predictive quality and so on), require specialized models for their custom products and so always face difficulties in providing a large number of randomized conditioned instances of their objects. The primary reason is that the process of capturing randomized conditioned images of real objects is usually costly, time-consuming, and challenging in practice. Due to the efficiency gained so far via the use of synthetic data for training such systems, synthetic data has recently attracted considerable attention. This paper presents an end-to-end synthetic data generation method for building a robust object detection model for customized products using NVIDIA Omniverse and CNNs. In this paper, we demonstrate and evaluate our contribution to the modeling of chess pieces, where a total accuracy of 98.8 % was obtained.

Index Terms—Object detection, Omniverse, synthetic data generation, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), NVIDIA

I. INTRODUCTION

In object detection systems, a model for an object class is derived from a set of training examples. For a fixed rigid object, only one example may be required, however, to capture certain aspects of class variability, multiple examples are often needed (often hundreds or thousands) [1]. In general, less training data is required when the model incorporates explicit information about class variability. In spite of this, it is difficult to formulate models that are able to capture the large variability present in images. The use of convolutional

neural networks (CNNs) which are capable of learning about class variability from large datasets is an alternative approach [2]. As opposed to the traditional handcrafted training samples provisioning approaches, an automated approach would help extensively in the speed, cost, accuracy, diversity, reliability, scalability and generalizability of the data acquisition process [3]. As a result of an automated synthetic data generation process, human efforts will be reduced in addition to human error, while monotonous labelling will be eliminated. However, a robust object detection with CNNs requires training data of varied and random combinations for background, camera angle, lighting conditions, distortions and so on [3]. While there have been several attempts in the past to generate synthetic data for the purpose of object detection (as discussed briefly in section 2), automated generation of synthetic data using 3D objects retrieved from 3D scanning techniques has not received appropriate attention. It is important to note that many works in the literature do not create synthetic images, while rather manipulate real images. We offer the complete end-to-end workflow for the task. Unlike the common blender method [4], which requires a long custom scripting process, our approach takes only a few steps for completion. As a result of our photorealistic rendering process, the appearance gap is nearly eliminated.

In this paper, we apply this end-to-end workflow to detecting chess figures as representative of many other tasks. The motivation to recognize chess pieces on a chess board was ultimately a chess robot for demonstration purposes for robotics and AI, based on the ABB YuMi (Fig. 1).

This research was motivated by the desire to construct a chess playing robot for demonstration purposes for robotics and artificial intelligence in our smart Production Systems lab at HTW Dresden, using the ABB YuMi robot shown in Fig. 1.

This robot is capable of playing against a human by grabbing chess pieces and moving them to another position using its actuators. For this purpose, it must be able to recognize the chess figures visually, as well as the location at which the figure stands. The existing method, however, is based solely on image comparison and is unable to cope with changes in

Fig. 1. ABB YuMi for playing chess

lighting conditions. As described in section II, the creation of a robust but manually generated data set can be extremely time-consuming. A further disadvantage of the image comparison approach is that it can only be applied to chessboards, where all pieces are in their starting positions, i.e. the robot knows where all figures are at the beginning of the game.

Synthetic data generation has applications in a wide variety of areas including improving traffic sign recognition [5], thermal infrared tracking [6], pedestrian counting [7], steel defect detection [8], industrial object detection and pose estimation [9], small target detection for search and rescue operations [10], X-Ray imaging [11] and so on. In practice, there are a number of challenges associated with dealing with image data, and in particular for object detection. Numerous studies have been conducted on the generation of synthetic images for the purpose of training in object detection. In [4], using the Open Source 3D creation suite Blender, the authors generated synthetic 3D objects where randomization was applied to position, orientation, and lighting conditions. However, they used 3D models that were constructed virtually by software, which often has difficulty accounting for fine physical details on objects. In [12], the authors used 3D CAD models and used depth data with domain-based background randomized noise to train a CNN for pose estimation. In [13], the authors presented a synthetic data generation approach for tobacco pack classification using image fusion. The 3D models for tobacco packs are built via manipulating the sides of the 3d cubes and combining alternatives of the two existing classes of tobacco packs, also to provide a balance by increasing the number of images for the minority class, as the secondary objective. A method presented in [14] incorporates cluttered images combined with 3D objects as well as distorted virtual backgrounds to generate synthetic data for object detection. The work presented in [9], instead of CAD models, makes use of image to image translation and edge maps extracted by mesh model projection, along with virtual backgrounds

to generate synthetic images for industrial object detection and pose estimation. In [15], synthetic data generation was studied for pedestrian detection, re-identification, segmentation, and tracking that used a video gaming environment for environment simulation. In [16], the authors used synthetic data for object detection to enable cluttered food grasping with adaptive fingers. In order to create a high-quality 3D model of each food item, the authors used the technology provided by Preferred Networks, Inc.

In spite of numerous attempts in the past for generating synthetic data for object detection, however, no particular attention has been paid to an automated generation of synthetic data using 3D objects obtained from 3D scanning. In the following section, we propose an end to end workflow for synthetic data generation based on 3d scanning of objects for providing a robust object detection.

II. METHODOLOGY

In short, we mainly use CNNs for image recognition. CNNs are built like the standard neural networks in layers, while the formation and sequencing of these layers are based on image kernels, which scan the image and detect local features from low to high levels. Since the robustness of CNNs depends largely on the data set used, the data must be as diverse as possible. In order to enable robust recognition in different environments and under different lighting situations, the domain in which the objects are located and how the object is arranged in it must be randomized, the so called Domain randomization (DR). This can only be achieved by randomizing several parameters, such as light conditions, chess figures arrangement, camera position, background objects, or the appearance of materials. Taking all this into account, it quickly becomes very time-consuming to create such a dataset with real captured images.

Assuming the **Handcrafted approach** takes about 30s per images for image acquisition, labelling (15 objects per image) about 1 minute and reviewing 30s per image, one image takes approx. 2 minutes. Assuming there has to be 10k images, the recording would take about 10 days, the labelling and reviewing 20 days. In sum, it would be 40 days in total. The training of a CNNs is straightforward nowadays and nearly automated. With current hardware it takes a few hours.

In the **Synthetic approach**, the step of image acquisition and data labelling merges into one step, as the computer generates the image and the labels at the same time. With medium render quality, a reasonably up-to-date workstation needs only a few seconds for generating one image including labels. To extrapolate it again to 10k images, acquisition and labelling takes only a couple of hours. The CNN training process is again straightforward to the handcrafted approach.

To successfully create robust object detection networks with the help of synthetic training data, the following end-to-end workflow is proposed, which is also represented in Fig. 2:

Fig. 2. Proposed End-To-End workflow for building a robust object detection network with the help of synthetic training data.

- 1) Creation of a validation set, consisting of real target images
- 2) Gathering and preparation of 3D-assets (target and environment assets)
- 3) Arranging of the scene and assets in Omniverse
- 4) Applying the randomizations in Omniverse
- 5) Rendering the synthetic images in Omniverse
- 6) Preparing the labeled data for the target CNN architecture
- 7) Train and evaluate the CNN
- 8) Put the model in Production

These steps are described in detail below:

A. Validation dataset

In order to obtain a qualitative statement about the ability of the CNNs to recognise the real during the training, a validation dataset has to be recorded. The literature often mentioned that the validation dataset has to be 20% of all images, but due to the fact that many more images can be generated synthetically, 5-10% are also sufficient. Care must be taken that the objects are always placed randomly and gathered in different light situations such as in different environments. Afterwards, the objects must be labelled and reviewed again, due to human errors in the labelling process.

B. 3D-Models

The basis for synthetic datasets are 3D models of the objects that need to be recognised and the background objects for arranging the scene. 3D models can be incorporated in the software (Omniverse) in many different ways, for instance as existing CAD model, 3D-scanned object or as synthetic generated 3D model. To prepare the 3D models, it may be

necessary to pre-process them in a 3D editing software, such as Blender. After all 3D assets are collected and cleaned, they can be exported to Omniverse using the Pixar's USD standard.

C. Omniverse

As a result of Omniverse's ability to combine the two worlds of simulation and creation of a digital twin with photorealistic graphics, it is often used in industrial metaverse applications, nowadays. In the past, CNNs training data was created using 3D software such as Blender, Maya, and Unity. Even with these tools, however, it was always necessary to put considerable manual efforts in order to arrange the scenes, randomize them, and create labels for them. As a result, for decades it was necessary to choose between rendering photorealistic images and simulating process flows with digital twins. Synthetic training data is often generated by using the Replicator API within the Omniverse code app. The first step, in this regard, is to load and arrange all the assets. There are two parts to the assets: the part that needs to be recognized and the part that forms the 3D environment in which the objects to be recognized are situated. For the environment's background, the Nvidia asset library is a suitable starting point. A total of almost 2000 objects are included in different categories. In order to enable robust detection even on real images, the Sim2Real Domain Gap must be overcome, which is divided into two sub-areas:

Appearance gap: The pixel level differences between two images. These differences can be a result of differences in object detail, materials, or in the case of synthetic data, differences in the capabilities of the rendering system used. Experiments have shown that the medium quality path tracking renderer might be a good trade off between quality and computing time. There is a clear increase in quality between the realtime renderer (Figure 3) and interactive renderer (Figure 4). The shadows and reflections are rendered more realistically by path-tracing. The difference between the interactive renderer (Figure 4) and the accurate renderer (Figure 5) is not very big, only a few more reflections are visible. The real-time renderer needs only 15ms, the interactive renderer 2s and the accurate renderer 10s per image, depending on what is shown in the scene. In conclusion, the interactive renderer might a good trade off between speed and quality.

Content gap: refers to the difference between the domains. This includes factors like the number of objects in the scene, their diversity of type and placement, and similar contextual information. A critical tool for overcoming the content gap is domain randomization (DR), which increases the size of the domain generated for a synthetic dataset. DR helps ensure that we include the range that best matches the reality, including anomalies. Applying DR in real world examples is significantly costly, as the domain would have to be changed in each image. Omniverse offers a powerful tool to carry out such randomization, with the Replicator API. Randomization is to be conducted for the following aspects:

- 1) Placement, scaling and orientation of all objects.

Fig. 3. Realtime Rendering Mode

Fig. 4. Interactive Rendering Mode

Fig. 6. RGB image

Fig. 7. Bounding Box annotation

- 2) Using the material definition language (MDL), every aspect of a texture can be changed, e.g. colour, reflectivity, surface roughness, etc.
- 3) The placement, shape and orientation of the light sources can be adjusted, as well as parameters such as light intensity and colour temperature.
- 4) Placement and attributes of the cameras (focal length, aperture, ISO, etc.)
- 5) Random objects from previously defined sets can be loaded and placed.

After all the randomisation steps are taken, the images can be rendered. This can be accomplished using the Omniverse Code UI or in batch mode. In batch mode, images are generated without any user interface, which has the advantage of enabling GPUs to be used for this purpose, such as the NVIDIA A100. The number of images rendered depends on the application. In the case of chess pieces (as the focus of this study), a total number of 1000 images are sufficient to enable robust recognition (Section II-A). Beside the normal RGB output (Figure 6, Omniverse can render a large number of representation forms, like bounding boxes (2D and 3D) in Fig. 7, instance and semantic segmentation masks in Fig. 8 or normal maps in Fig. 9.

Fig. 5. Accurate Rendering mode

D. Training

Sometimes it may be necessary, to convert the resulting labels into the format compatible with the CNN used, since Omniverse exports data in an proprietary way, different to famous neuronal net annotation formats, such as MS COCO, PASCAL VOC or YOLO. Training CNNs is nowadays straightforward and depends largely on the used architecture. The famous CNN architectures for object detection are: YOLOv5, SSD, RetinaNet and MaskRCNN. To put the model into production, it may be helpful to convert it into a specific inference library, such as TensorRT or OpenVino. The deployment depends strongly on the purpose. For a CNN running centrally in a cloud or fog environment, the Triton inference server from

Fig. 8. Segmentation Mask annotation

Fig. 9. Normal Map

Fig. 10. Scanning of the chess figures

NVIDIA may be a good choice. For a model running locally at the edge, the NVIDIA Jetson may be a good option.

III. EVALUATION

A. Experimental Setup

1) *Training dataset:* As described in section II-B, the 3D assets can be obtained in different ways. Our chess figures were scanned using a 3D scanner (Einscan Pro 2x), like in Fig. 10. Afterwards, the 3D model was cleaned up in Blender, i.e. the triangles in the mesh grid were reduced by a factor of 10, the pivot point, which represents the anchor point of the mesh, was set to the same position for all the objects and some deletions and unevenness were corrected. The chessboard was modeled and textured in Blender based on the photos taken by the camera. Since Omniverse works based on the USD file format, the assets were exported from Blender into this format, to load and arrange them in Omniverse. Scenery objects in the background, such as tables, chairs, newspapers, ladders, etc come entirely from NVIDIA's asset library. As mentioned above in section II-C, the domain of the dataset has to be randomized, and as a result, the following steps have been applied to the chess figures:

- 1) To generate valid chess situations, python-chess was integrated into Replicator. During data generation, two competing chess AI agents play against each other and produce valid chess moves.
- 2) As base materials, *Wood Tiles Ash* was used for the white figures and *Wood Tiles Walnut* for the black figures from the Nvidia material library. Fig. 11 represents different variations of the material *Wood Tiles Ash*, where the following attributes of the material were randomized: *wood color, coating reflectivity, floor brightness* and *tiles base roughness*.
- 3) 10 sphere-lights with randomized intensity temperature (4000k to 6500k) were randomly placed around the chess board.
- 4) The camera was randomly placed on parametrically created spheres with different diameters around the chessboard.
- 5) The environment was randomized by placing random tables under the chessboard and random environment prop around this.
- 6) The texture of the floor and wall was randomly changed.

Fig. 11. Example of different materials on the chess figure

kw	-	king white
qw	-	queen white
bw	-	bishop white
kw	-	knight white
rw	-	rock white
pw	-	pawn white
kb	-	king black
qb	-	queen black
bb	-	bishop black
Kb	-	knight black
rb	-	rock black
pb	-	pawn black

Fig. 12. Example of a picture from the validation dataset with labels

A total of 25k images with 12 different classes (each figure type for a black class and a white class) were generated in batch mode. The images were rendered in a resolution of 1024x1024 with a medium-quality interactive renderer. The render times were about 4s per image, depending on what is on the image. A workstation with the following specifications was used to create the dataset: 2x Intel Xeon Gold 6254, 2x Nvidia RTX 6000, 256 GB RAM. The actual RGB images, bounding boxes, as well as the instance and semantic segmentation masks were recorded. The dataset was divided into different sizes (100, 500, 1k, 5k, 10k, 25k) by randomly selecting images from the entire dataset.

2) *Validation dataset:* As mentioned in section II-A, 200 pictures were taken by the camera, whereby care was taken that the chess pieces were always placed randomly, that different light situations were covered and that the chess board was located in different environmental variations. To make this possible, the validation set was recorded at different locations at different times during the day in order to include different lighting and environmental situations in the data set. Each image took an average of 30 seconds to capture. In the next step, the bounding boxes of the chess pieces were labelled, which also took about 1-2 minutes per image, depending on how many chess figures were placed on the chessboard. In total, the creation of the dataset took around 6-7h (see Fig. 12).

3) *Training:* In this study, we used YOLOv5 with MS COCO to implement the proposed method, due to its wide applications and popularity in the relevant literature. The

bounding boxes were converted from the proprietary Repliator format to the YOLOv5 format. Each dataset was incorporated for training with different expansions (nano, small, medium, large, extra-large) of the YOLOv5 network, which simply reflects the number of layers and parameters, ascending from nano to extra-large. The dataset with 25k images was incorporated in the training process with 15 epochs, an image size of 1024x1024 and a learning rate of 0.001. Batch size was automatically determined by the number of parameters in the network and the amount of available GPU memory. The number of epochs was scaled up for variants with smaller data sets. In addition, the YOLOv5 library has been used to implement data augmentation. However, data augmentation is unlikely to bring a significant improvement, since the large degree of diversity in the proposed synthetic dataset will naturally lead to more significant generalizability than augmentation. The corresponding code for proposed methodology has been provided for public use at [17].

B. Experimental Results

Intersection over unit (IoU) is a commonly used metric based on the overlapping area between the ground through bounding box (GT) and the prediction bounding box (PR). The IoU threshold determines the percentage value above which the bounding-box is counted as a true positive (TP) or false positive (FP). In the following, an IoU threshold value of 0.5 is considered which indicates the average precision ($AP@05$). As mentioned above in section III-A1, the entire dataset was split into smaller subsets to identify which number of images are sufficient to enable robust recognition. The highest score / $AP@05$ of 98.8% was achieved with the extra-large expansion and 10k training set, as shown in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14. These figures also reveal that 1000 images (98.8% $AP@05$) are sufficient to provide nearly equally robust detection as with the 10k set. Increasing the data set size up to 25k images has not led to improvements, moreover the $AP@05$ of smaller network expansions (nano and small) decreases again with increasing dataset size from 5k, see also in Fig. 14. This could be due to the fact that smaller expansions can hold less information due to their smaller number of parameters. The smaller networks do not capture the essential characteristics of the chess figure as a result of the attempt to generalise to other situations. These networks overfit to the training set, which can be seen in Fig. 15. The training loss for the extra-large and nano expansions are almost the same, but the validation loss for the nano is significantly worse.

From the medium architecture onwards, a plateau increase can be observed. The results only improves from 98.1% (medium@1000 images) to 98.8% (extra-large@1000 images). Therefore, the medium version of YOLOv5 architecture with 1000 images would be the appropriate trade off between the recognition speed and precision. Fig. 16 and Fig. 17 exhibit that the loss curve is much smoother with more images than with fewer images. The network with fewer images shows variable performance due to the smaller domain space. What finally worth mentioning is that even with only 100 images, an

Fig. 13. confusion matrix between the YOLO expansion size and the size of the dataset

Fig. 14. $AP@05$ vs. dataset size

Fig. 15. loss between nano and extra-large network expansion

Fig. 16. train loss with a dataset size of 100 images

Fig. 17. train loss with a dataset size of 5000 images

Fig. 18. Examples of the detected car parts from the demonstrator

$AP@05$ of 95.6% has already been achieved. This may be due to the fact that the images already cover a very large domain space due to the DR, which allows the CNN to concentrate on the essential features of the chess figures.

C. Generalizability

In order to examine generalizability, the presented approach was examined on a demonstrator that replicates a mini production line in an automotive manufacturing system. The parts of the cars are visually recognized, i.e. for assembly control or quality inspections (Fig. 18). For this purpose, the same approach was incorporated through the use of 3D models of the cars. A dataset of 40k images (10k from each side) of 3 different cars with 15 classes each was generated in NVIDIA Omniverse. The training process was carried out with the same parameters as the case of the chess figures. With the extra-large expansion of YOLOv5, an $AP@05$ of 94.9% was achieved.

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V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented an end to end workflow for synthetic data generation based on a 3D scanning of objects. This study focuses on an automated generation of synthetic images to provide appropriate training data both in terms of quality and quantity, required for a robust implementation of object detection applications. The core of this work, was using

NVIDIA Omniverse to simulate varieties of conditions for the synthetic images on the ground of an initial 3D scan of custom products/ objects. In particular, this would eliminate the need for a manual image capturing of varied conditions in real environments which is difficult for private companies. In this research, the proposed method was applied to the synthetic images of chess figures. With 98.8 % in the accuracy of object detection, the results demonstrate a significant performance for the proposed method for synthetic image generation.

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